

4D Data Organization and Alignment at World Scale

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Abstract

A current challenge related to 4D viewers at world scale is the low number and geographic and temporal coverage of 3D models available. To overcome this issue, we work on different tools to (1) harvest 3D models, images, and location-based information from multiple sources via automated and community-based approaches; (2) automatically process these into 4D cityscape models; (3) make the 4D models accessible in two visualizations: via a 4D browser and a location-dependent augmented reality representation. Since previous articles report on the pipeline, tools, and usage scenarios, this contribution highlights ongoing developments in (1) large-scale 3D data retrieval; (2) 3D mesh model and LiDAR processing; and (3) novel view synthesis via Gaussian Splatting. The datasets are viewed in two 4D world viewers for (4) desktop browsing and (5) location-based mobile use. To date, they have been tested in seven countries.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → Digital libraries and archives; Architecture (buildings); • **Computing methodologies** → Computer vision;

1. Introduction

Since 2016, our group has developed a modular 4D world viewer framework for spatiotemporal content browsing on mobile and desktop devices [MMB*24]. The 4D City application (<https://4dcity.org>) enables time-variant virtual 3D impressions of historic cities on mobile devices. It enables virtual city tours and past-plays, e.g., mixed-reality escape or discovery games, and provides access to knowledge assets from open-source platforms such as Wikipedia or tourist information platforms. Unique features of that application include a dynamic shader, which can create the 4D environments on the fly. The 4D browser (<https://4dbrowser.org>) enables search and browsing through media collections on desktop devices. Linking digital images and their actual location allows users, e.g., to directly present resources, which proves a valuable support tool for historical research. Users of the virtual archives can benefit extensively from effective search functions and tools, which are not only content- and theme-based but also location-based.

A current challenge in the process of scaling up these 4D viewers to world scale is the low number and geographic and temporal coverage of 3D models available. To overcome this issue, we work on different tools to (1) harvest 3D models, images, and location-based information from multiple sources and via automated and community-based approaches; (2) automatically process these into 4D cityscape models. Since previous articles report on the pipeline, tools, and usage scenarios, this contribution is dedicated to highlighting ongoing developments in (1) large-scale 3D data retrieval;

(2) 3D mesh model and LiDAR processing; and (3) novel view synthesis via Gaussian Splatting.

2. Data collection

To gather data on the world scale, we set up a server-side pipeline to retrieve data from different providers. Data retrieval comprises (1) building footprints from Open Street Map (OSM), which are parametrically extruded into 3D LOD-1 (Level of Detail) models, and (2) a world-scale digital elevation model with a 50 m grid from SRTM data. Higher-detail 3D mesh geometries have been retrieved from various sources and stored in Zenodo via a multi-stage content processing pipeline [MBD*24]. The current datasets are shown in Table 1.

Content classification of the retrieved 3D data was utilized to identify non-cultural heritage and location-based objects, such as buildings and sculptures. The classification was done via Python server-side scripts that iterate through the rendered images. Free text-image classification of these images was performed via Google Cloud Vision with the 10 most probable categories per image retrieved and via LLaVA-NeXT / Mistral 7B with the top 5 categories identified. For location recognition, we employed various LLMs (Deepseek-R1, Llama 3.2 3B, QWEN+R1 Dist. 1.5B) to retrieve locations from captions and Google Cloud Vision API, PLONK, GeoCLIP, and OrienterNET to retrieve location information from images.

Data source	No.	Description
Europeana	8,708	The Europeana 3D metadata was retrieved via the Europeana Python Framework in 03/2025.
Objaverse 1.0	55,614	The Objaverse 1.0 dataset includes 800,000 3D objects. Of these, those we selected, which are classified as Cultural Heritage, were retrieved in our projects.
5DCulture	8,406	The 5DCulture dataset was compiled in the eponymous project in 2024. The dataset includes various mainly low-poly models of single buildings of different age in the cities of Trento, Sion, Amsterdam, Dresden and Jena.
Smithsonian	2,407	A set of models from the Smithsonian museum is included in the Objaverse-XL dataset.
MegaScenes	431,035	A set of photogrammetric reconstructions of landmarks worldwide [TCC*25].
Segmented and Google 3D tiles	LiDAR	We segmented these tiles and utilized them for training via their OSM footprints.

Table 1: 3D data sources.

3. Data processing

Recent approaches focus on the 3D spatial visualization of contemporary city scenes via view synthesis (recent overview: [MBS*24]) or parametric 3D model generation (e.g., [ZZW*24]). Our approach uses images that were both digitally and non-digitally created to parametrically reconstruct time-varying 4D models of the city. In comparison to previous approaches (e.g., [BBDV20]), our focus is on processing in-the-wild data.

The model creation pipeline starts with a baseline view. First, we create building geometries parametrically from building footprints (Figure 1a). This step is currently done semi-automatically for historical plans (described in [MMB*24]) and uses the already vectorized OSM building layer to retrieve and process contemporary buildings at large scale. In the next step, we create the 3D building by extruding the footprints of building walls and calculating the roof shape. Where photographic material is available, in another pipeline step we target the spatialization of photographs and map the photographs onto the facade according to the calculated position and orientation (Figure 1b). Where available, we replace the low-detail OSM models with higher-resolution 3D mesh models of either entire cities (Figure 1c) or specific objects, e.g., sculptures (Figure 1d). For those meshes, we calculate bounding boxes and do not show OSM structures within these boxes.

3.1. 3D processing tasks

To support the inclusion of 3D meshes from heterogeneous sources, we developed and use a set of 3D processing tools. Reality-based

Figure 1: 4D model, viewport examples.

data such as photogrammetric reconstructions or LiDAR scans cover large areas and multiple buildings as well as nuisances like trees, cars, or other artifacts. For our scenario, it is necessary to segment this complex, unstructured 3D data into single buildings [MMB*24]. In general, building footprints from OSM are utilized to identify individual buildings and extract their corresponding 3D geometry from the data as a preliminary step for subsequent processing (Figure 2).

Figure 2: LiDAR data for Jena, Germany (left), OSM building footprints used to crop out buildings (middle), buildings separated from the 3D tiles (right).

3D tile segmentation: One source of 3D meshes is Google 3D tiles. Every footprint polygon from the OSM is padded slightly with an offset to ensure full capturing of the building in the 3D mesh model. The individual buildings are then segmented via a Boolean operation using a scripted Blender process. The calculation of the Boolean operation is significantly influenced by the size of the 3D tiles (Table 2). The larger the 3D tile, the longer it takes to calculate the operation. Hence, we optimized the import and calculation by splitting the imported 3D tile into smaller sections. We check which sections of the tiles are intersected by each building and only these smaller sections are used for the Boolean operation, instead of the whole tile.

3D mesh to ground projection: A common issue with photogrammetric reconstructions is that building models often do not fit to a digital elevation model and therefore need to be fused with

Tile size	Low	Medium	High
100 x 100 m	~ 1 sec	~ 2 sec	~ 3 sec
200 x 200 m	~ 2 sec	~ 3 sec	~ 7 sec
400 x 400 m	~ 27 sec	~ 50 sec	~ 256 sec
700 x 500 m (optimized)	~ 1 sec	~ 2.5 sec	~ 3.5 sec

Table 2: Processing times of the Boolean operation per building in specified quality and tile size with an inefficient and optimized method.

different, corresponding boundaries. Various approaches are available for multi-resolution meshes and mesh blending [BBDV20]. Due to the high level of heterogeneity and robustness needed for our application scenario, we developed a straightforward algorithm to facilitate adaptation of the photogrammetric model’s environment to the ground. It comprised the steps of (1) detecting building vertices, (2) shifting the building’s ground vertices to the terrain, and (3) projecting the environment vertices onto the terrain plane.

As a first step, the OSM building footprint of the building is placed within the scene. An iteration is performed over all vertices of the model. For each vertex, a ray is cast perpendicularly downward. If it hits the OSM plane, the vertex is saved as a building vertex, if not, it is saved as environment. To fit the building to the terrain, the deepest vertex of all building vertices is calculated and the distance to the ground determined. The whole model is then shifted to the ground plane according to the distance. In this way, the building is placed well and the environment placement remains. The last step is repeated by an iteration and a ray casting. The distance between the environment vertices and the terrain is determined and the single vertex is shifted by the specific distance. This results in projection of the environment onto the terrain. As a variant, we tested a weighted projection, where boundary vertices are gradually blended to the ground (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Comparison of the projection methods. Left: Projection to the ground by distance. Right: Weighted projection.

LiDAR roof detection: The LiDAR point cloud extracted for each building via OSM footprints is used to segment and identify planes. To detect planar segments by fitting geometric primitives, we use the Efficient RANSAC Shape Detection algorithm from CloudCompare [Clo22]. While this method shows great potential for creating dimensionally accurate roof geometries (Figure 4), certain limitations must be considered. The identification of the planes

heavily depends on careful selection of parameters that may need to be iterated to obtain the desired segmentation of the roof. These parameters may vary in different urban contexts. Factors such as roof types, slope angles, and point density drastically influence the choice of parameter values.

Figure 4: Segmented roof planes extracted from LiDAR point cloud data using Efficient RANSAC Shape Detection. Each color represents an individual planar segment corresponding to roof facets of the building.

Moreover, it is not guaranteed that a certain set of parameters will yield optimal results across all buildings within a city. If the parameters are too relaxed, the result is sometimes under-segmentation that fails to capture roof complexity. In contrast, strict values may cause over-segmentation and fragmentation of roof facets. Despite these challenges, the approach offers a scalable and adaptable solution for enhancing the geometric fidelity of 3D city models within the broader 4D data framework. Six different roofs were evaluated. Across all of them, the fitted planes achieved an average mean distance of +0.0126 meters (StdDev = 0.1369 meters), with an overall inlier ratio of 57.7 %.

3.2. Image-based modeling via Gaussian Splatting

To create 3D mesh models from historical images, we are currently investigating several methods. For testing, we employ a set of 1,305 images of historic Budapest, which are registered into a single continuous model covering an area of approximately 2.56 km² and several smaller disconnected parts (e.g., individual squares or buildings).

We investigated two hyperparameters for initialization of SDF-based methods (NeuS in the Wild [SCW*22] and Neusfacto-Angelo [LME*23]) with an initial bounding box and initial bias parameter of 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.8, 1.0 (Figure 5). Due to the randomness in the optimization process, the results are not deterministic. NeuS in the Wild achieves very fine details in the facade configuration and good overall quality on the building, but the surrounding buildings do not have high-quality geometry. Using the Neusfacto-Angelo model, we achieved good overall geometry, even for the backgrounds. We found that even for fine details it is advantageous to use a large bounding box. This is because the optimization uses the empty space to “store” inconsistent geometry between images. Without it, the model has no place to correct for imperfections or inconsistencies in the input images.

Mesh generation from sparse images is limited by the input data. To get high-quality novel views in real time, we investigate Gaussian Splatting [KKLD23] with geometric priors from the SDF-

Figure 5: Examples of different initial values of bias parameter: 0.3, 0.7 and 1.0 (left to right).

based methods from above (Figure 6). Unlike NeuS-based methods and to an extent NeRF-based methods [MST*20], Gaussian Splatting does not utilize geometric information during optimization. The former traces along image rays and accumulates density/radiance in space, while Gaussian Splatting only projects the gaussians into the image plane. This is prone to overfitting especially for sparse images. Even though the gaussians are initialized at the sparse point cloud from SfM, the optimization overfits to individual training views by generating “noise” in free space. To clean up the free space and reduce overfitting, we use the previous Angelo model to render depth maps and add a simple depth loss term to the optimization.

Figure 6: Different bounding boxes used for mesh generation.

4. Conclusion

In the current state, the 4D retrieval and modeling pipelines are not fully optimized nor validated for the full dataset. The next step will be to complete the pipeline, development, and re-use via testable datasets to benchmark the pipeline steps. The plan is to further validate the LiDAR roof detection method as an agent competing against other roof generators already developed in our pipeline: the OSM parametric modeler and satellite image-based roof extraction methods. Our envisioned pipeline includes these three meth-

ods, which function as agents tasked with generating candidate roof shapes for buildings. The final geometry will be chosen based on a weighted evaluation of geometric accuracy and data completeness. For the Gaussian Splats, the fusion between the 3D mesh models and the splats is envisioned to enable cross-validation between the depth maps generated by splatting and depth maps calculated from the 4D application viewports from extruded map geometries. Besides, all these application scenarios are on the way to be implemented and utilized as a test case.

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